

#26

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

SOCIAL NETWORK ANALYSIS

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>To be used iteratively throughout the project/initiative to assess and improve network membership and collaborative relationships.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small to large multi actor group.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>Basic Microsoft Excel skills required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>½ day each time the evaluation is done (depending on group size & extent of discussion needed internally or/and with stakeholders). The interpretation may take another ½ day or more.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Very low, requires basic materials. Can be conducted physically with internal/ external participants in a room or on an online platform such as Klaxoon, Pinup, or Mural. The online option can also be used to simply fill the matrix of relationships (see Excel template). At least one facilitator is required.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 2, 3.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Identify crucial actors that shape the network and/or boost the innovation
- Identify actors that negatively affect the actors and/or undermine the innovation
- Monitor the way the network develop and adapt the strategy/activities accordingly.

Background and Logic

The idea is to evaluate interactive innovation projects in terms of the role of actors' interactivity in relation to decision-making on the innovation process (through information or knowledge exchange, and joint or cooperative research). This can be for example about the role of an actor that entered in the course of the process and that strengthened the innovation through establishing suitable connections with other actors, leading to a better decision-making process on the innovation.

The analysis of the network of actors can be made at one point of time only, or at 2 or 3 consecutive periods of time. We recommend the latter as it allows us to see the evolution of the network of actors over time.

The evaluation can be done in quasi real time, but also in an ex-post manner. An ex-post assessment means that the evaluator will reconstruct the network as it was at the period of interest.

In terms of data source, three options are possible:

- The evaluator makes its own estimation of relationship level between the actors;
- The evaluator involve key actors to estimate the levels of relationships; or
- He/she asks the actors involved in the network, what their levels of relationships with the other actors are. In this case, bilateral exchanges are generally recommended. However, if actors feel or would feel comfortable to discuss this together, for example in case there is no major power asymmetries or conflicts between actors, a workshop could also be performed.

The choice between the three above options should be based on three criteria: (1) time investment, (2) financial and human resources, and (3) the degree of knowledge of the auditor and other actors on how the network's actors are connected to each other.

Materials

- Flipchart paper
- If a workshop with stakeholders is implanted:
 - » Sticky notes
 - » Thick dark markers

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1

- In case a workshop is conducted, explain the purpose, logic and background of the exercise.
- Ask participants to write their name and an 'actor identifier' on a sticky note (either physically in an in-person meeting or virtually, using an appropriate platform such as Klaxoon, Mural, Pinup etc.)
- Actor identifiers depend on the orientation of the multi-actor project. For example, in a Horizon 2020 Thematic Network, the actor identifiers may include research, education, SME and extension. The diversity of actors (and their actor identifiers) are typically cited in funding applications, as a credential of the project's multi-actor approach. The group can be reminded of the importance of including different actor categories, and asked to reflect on the actor category they are representing in the group/network/project
- It is important to explain to the group that some actors may have other/several actor identifiers. Ask them to reflect on the particular role/s they will/ have in the project in choosing their actor identifiers. They may choose more than one identifier, but it is important for actors to represent the actor category/ies they are representing in the project/ assigned in a grant agreement, where relevant.

Step 2

Step 2 only applies if the evaluator decides to draw the map of actors. Otherwise, the evaluator should go directly to step 3.

Before drawing the map of actors, the scale of relationships should be selected. The scale corresponds to the number of possible relationship levels. The relationship level corresponds to the level of interactivity in relation to decision-making on the innovation (through information / knowledge exchange, and joint or cooperative research) throughout the innovation process. The evaluator should select a scale of 3, 4, or 5 levels. A scale of 3 levels, for instance, means that any existing relationships can be of minor (1), medium, (2), or high level (3). The other possible scales work on the same principle, with (1) being the lowest level of existing relationships. In any case, when no relationship exist between two actors, the level of relationships is considered to be (0).

The drawing of the map of actors can either be done internally or with stakeholders in a workshop setting. The name of the actors should be written/specified on separate sticky notes, and arrows should also be constructed in order to link the actors. Arrows of different colours should be constructed in order to represent the different levels of relationships (e.g. 'green' for level 1, 'blue' for level 2). The map of actors is then drawn (time: 45-60 min) by stakeholders in groups of maximum 6 participants. This means that there can be multiple groups. If that is the case, each group should be as diverse as possible in terms of types of actors involved. Once the groups have finalised the drawing, one person from each group presents the map of actors to the attendees (time: 5-10 min for each group). This should include a short discussion session after each presentation.

The drawing can be made at one point of time only, or at 2 or 3 consecutive periods of time. We recommend the latter as it allows us to see the evolution of the network of actors over time.

Step 3

The Excel evaluation tool should be used to enter data and be able to interpret results in a more detailed manner. This should be done internally. Data should be based on step 2, if the latter was performed. Otherwise, data is directly entered in the Excel file.

The analysis of the network of actors can be made at one point of time only, or at 2 or 3 consecutive periods of time. We recommend the latter as it allows us to see the evolution of the network of actors over time.

The Excel file refers to 3 possible time periods: Periods 'A', 'B' and 'C'. The evaluator should start with period 'A', corresponding to the first period of time, he/she wants to evaluate the quality of the network of actors.

The following Excel 'how to guide' is split into four consecutive parts:

- Periods 'A'
- Period 'B'
- Period 'C'
- Summary

Period 'A'

FIRST TAB - 'Actors_pA'

First the scale of relationships should be specified in the tab 'Actors_pA'. The scale corresponds to the number of possible relationship levels. The relationship level corresponds to the level of interactivity in relation to decision-making on the innovation (through information / knowledge exchange, and joint or cooperative research) throughout the innovation process.

Please select the scale (3, 4 or 5)

Scale of relationships 4

Select scale of relationships by clicking here

The evaluator should select a scale of 3, 4, or 5 levels. A scale of 3 levels, for instance, means that any existing relationships can be of minor (1), medium, (2), or high level (3). The other possible scales work on the same principle, with (1) being the lowest level of existing relationships. In any case, when no relationship exists between two actors, the level of relationships is considered to be (0).

The network of actors under review can contain up to 46 actors. The list of actors should be specified in the tab 'Actors_pA'. Please note that **NO numbers** must be entered, only letters.

Please specify the list of network's actors	
Code	Actor
1	Example A
2	Example B
3	Example C
4	
5	
6	
7	
8	

Enter the list of actors in this column. **NO number should be entered to avoid potential Excel issues, only letters must be entered**

Once the scale of relationships as well as the list of actors are defined, the evaluator should click on '**COMPUTE**', so that the Excel file can process the information.

COMPUTE

Click here to compute

Note that most tabs contain the button '**COMPUTE**', triggering the Excel file to process the data entered (from all sheets). **Results will only be accurate if the last entered data has been processed.**

SECOND TAB - 'Matrix_pA'

Secondly, the evaluator should specify the level of relationships between each pair of actors in the tab 'Matrix_pA'. The scale corresponds to the number of possible levels of relationship. In the below example,

the selected scale of relationships was 4, so each pair of existing relationship should be rated from 1 to 4. In the case of absence of relationships, the cell can be either left empty or be rated '0'.

Click here to compute once you entered the data.

'Problem Box':
If empty, there is no apparent issue

Fill the cells below the grey diagonal, corresponding to the level of relationships. If the defined scale is '4', the evaluator should enter a number from '1' to '4'. In case of no relationships, you can either leave the cell empty or specify '0'.

The rows for which the first column "actor" is coloured in black should not be filled out; they do not refer to any actors. All actors that were specified in the first tab 'Actors_pA' appear in the first column "Actor" of this tab 'Matrix_pA'.

Once the matrix (the half part below the grey diagonal) is filled out, the evaluator should click on 'COMPUTE' (on the top & left hand side) in order to process the data. Note that only the lowest half of the matrix has to be filled out, because the network is "undirected", meaning that we do not consider to what degree the exchange of information between actor 'A' and 'B' is directed by 'A' or 'B'. The relationship is considered as "interactive". The upper part of the Matrix is being filled out automatically after clicking on 'COMPUTE'.

THIRD TAB - 'PDist_pA'

The tab 'PDist_pA' indicates the so-called "partial distance" between each pair of actors, in a matrix format, based on the previous tab 'Matrix_pA'. No entry is required in this sheet; it indicates some preliminary results. The distance corresponds to the number of ties through which an actor should pass by to connect with another actor. The "partial distance" follows the same definition, except that it does not account for "distance" above '3'. If the actual "distance" between two actors is above '3', the "partial distance" refers to it as a "partial distance" of '3'. The reason for this are three folds:

- It considerably simplify the calculation of distance;
- Distances above '3' are rare in actors' network, and a high share of such high distances indicates a poor quality of network;
- We are interested in the evolution of the network's quality, rather than in the absolute value of distance or other indicators.

FOURTH TAB - 'Sum_pA'

The tab 'Sum_pA' indicates the results for the first period of time 'pA'. The upper part summarises the results for the overall network of actors. The indicators are as follows:

- **Number of Nodes:** Number of actors in the network;
- **Number of Ties:** Number of existing pairs of relationship in the network;
- **Average Degrees:** Average number of direct ties per actor; in other words, the average number of direct connections an actor has in the network;
- **Weighted Average Degrees:** Weighted average number of direct ties per actor, where each direct connection is weighted by the level of relationship;
- **Density:** Actual number of connections relative to the maximum possible number of connections in the network;
- **Weighted Density:** Weighted actual number of connections relative to the maximum possible number of connections in the network;
- **Partial Average Distance:** Average minimum number of ties required to connect two particular actors;
- **Adjusted Average Distance:** Average number of ties required to connect two particular actors when excluding distances of '3' and above;

- **Particular Room for Distance Improvement:** 'Partial average distance' minus 'adjusted average distance'. This indicates. The higher the number of distances of '3' or above, the higher the indicators 'particular room for distance improvement' is. Concretely, it indicates whether and to what extent the network could be significantly improved.

The results not only specify the actual value of each indicator, but also what the best possible value is and the level of "completeness". A "completeness" level of 100% means that the indicator in question cannot be improved. Some indicators have to be maximised while others should be minimised.

Indicators that should be maximised are:

- Average degrees
- Weighted average degrees
- Density
- Weighted density

Indicators that should be minimised are:

- Partial average distance
- Adjusted average distance
- 'Particular room for distance improvement'

COMPUTE	Coherence indicators (entire network)									
	Number of nodes	Number of ties	Average degrees	Weighted average degrees	Density	Weighted density	Partial average distance (each pair of distance capped to 3)	Adjusted average distance (excluding distances >=3)	Particular room for distance improvement ((Partial average distance) - (Adjusted average distance))	
Result - Value	3	4	1.33	1.33	0.67	0.17	1.33	1.33	0%	
Best possible value	#	6	2	8	1	1	1	1	#	
Result - Completeness	#	67%	67%	17%	67%	17%	#	#	#	

Indicators at actor level												
Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort
Code	Actor	Degrees	Weighted degrees	Density	Weighted density	Partial average distance	SD Partial average distance	Adjusted average distance	SD Adjusted average distance	Particular room for distance improvement ((Partial average distance) - (Adjusted average distance))		
1	Example A	1	1	0.50	0.13	1.50	0.71	1.50	0.71	0%		
3	Example C	1	1	0.50	0.13	1.50	0.71	1.50	0.71	0%		
2	Example B	2	2	1.00	0.25	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0%		
4												
5												
6												
7												
8												
9												
10												

The lower part specifies the indicators for each of the actors involved in the network. The indicators are the same as above, with the following additions:

- **SD Partial Average Distance:** Standard deviation of the 'partial average distance'; in other words, the heterogeneity of 'partial distance' a given actor has with the others.
- **SD Adjusted Average Distance:** Standard deviation of the 'adjusted partial average distance'; in other words, the heterogeneity of 'adjusted distance' a given actor has with the others.

Note that the evaluator has the option to sort the results (ascending) for each column by clicking on 'SORT'.

Code	Actor	Degrees	Weighted degrees
1	Example A	1	1
3	Example C	1	1
2	Example B	2	2
4			
5			
6			
7			
8			
9			
10			
11			
12			

FIFTH TAB - 'Gph_pA'

The tab 'Gph_pA' indicates the key results for the first period of time 'pA' in the form of graphs. The following indicators are represented:

- Degrees
- Weighted degrees
- Density
- Weighted density
- Partial distance
- Adjusted distance

For example, click here to sort the results in ascending order

Period 'B'

The same basic structure as period 'A' applies to period 'B'. The five tabs corresponding to period 'B' are labelled as follows: 'Actors_pB', 'Matrix_pB', 'PDist_pB', 'Sum_pB', and 'Gph_pB'.

The only difference between period 'A' and 'B' resides in tab 'Actors_pB'.

How to fill the tab 'Actors_pB'?

First, the level of relationships should be specified, as for the tab 'Actors_pA'. Note that if the specified level of relationships is not the same as for 'Actors_pA', the results between the first and second period of time (pA vs pB) would not all be comparable. In that case, the weighted scores (weighted average degrees and weighted density) cannot be compared between the two periods.

We strongly recommend the evaluator to specify the same level of relationships as for the first period 'A'.

The actors specified in the tab 'Actors_pA' are automatically transferred to the column "Actors Period A" in the present tab 'Actors_pB'. The evaluator should then specify in the column "Actor to be dropped?", whether or not some of the actors that were present at the first period of time are still present in the second period. In addition, the evaluator should specify which new actors eventually entered the network in the second period. New actors should be specified in the column "New actors Period B", and the entries should only start from a code number (column "Code") not already used. Below we illustrate a situation where a new actor, "Example D", entered the network in period B. You will notice that the entry is made at the row corresponding to Code n°4, which is the first code, in numerical order, that was not already used. Please note again that **NO numbers** must be entered, only letters.

The last column "All actors Period B" specifies the full list of actors in period B.

Code	Actors Period A	Actor to be dropped ?	New actors Period B (start entries from a Code number (column I) not already used)	All actors Period B
1	Example A	Yes		
2	Example B	No		Example B
3	Example C	No		Example C
4		No	Example D	Example D
5		No		
6		No		
7		No		
8		No		
9		No		
10		No		
11		No		

Enter the list of new actors for period B in this column. **NO number should be entered to avoid potential Excel issues, only letters must be entered**

Period 'C'

The same basic structure as period 'A' and 'B' applies to period 'C'. The five tabs corresponding to period 'C' are labelled as follows: 'Actors_pC', 'Matrix_pC', 'PDist_pC', 'Sum_pC', and 'Gph_pC'.

The only difference resides in tab 'Actors_pC'.

How to fill the tab 'Actors_pC'?

First, the level of relationships should be specified, as for the tab 'Actors_pA' and 'Actors_pB'. Note that if the specified level of relationships is not the same as for 'Actors_pA' or 'Actors_pB', the results between the successive periods of time would not all be comparable. In that case, the weighted scores (weighted average degrees and weighted density) cannot be compared between the periods.

We strongly recommend the evaluator to specify the same level of relationships as for the first period 'A' and second period 'B'.

The actors specified in the tab 'Actors_pB' are automatically transferred to the column "Actors Period C" in the present tab 'Actors_pC'. The evaluator should then specify in the column "Actor to be dropped?", whether or not some of the actors that were present in the second period of time are still present in the third period. In addition, the evaluator should specify which new actors eventually entered the network in the third period. New actors should be specified in the column "New actors Period C", and the entries should only start from a code number (column "Code") not already used. Below we illustrate a situation where a new actor, "Example E", entered the network in period C. You will notice that the entry is made at the row corresponding to Code n°5, which is the first code, in numerical order, that was not already used. Please note again that **NO numbers** must be entered, only letters.

The last column "All actors Period C" specifies the full list of actors in period C

Code	Actors Period B	Actor to be dropped ?	New actors Period C (start entries from a Code number (column	All actors Period C
1		No		
2	Example B	No		Example B
3	Example C	No		Example C
4	Example D	No		Example D
5		No	Example E	Example E
6		No		
7		No		
8		No		
9		No		
10		No		
11		No		
12		No		

Enter the list of new actors for period C in this column. **NO number should be entered to avoid potential Excel issues, only letters must be entered**

Summary

FIRST TAB - 'Sum'

All results from the periods 'A', 'B', and 'C' are specified in the tab 'sum'. The upper part indicates results for the overall network and each period.

COMPUTE									
Coherence indicators (entire network)									
Period A	Number of nodes	Number of ties	Average degrees	Weighted average degrees	Density	Weighted density	Partial average distance	Adjusted average distance	Particular room for distance improvement
Result - Value	3	4	1.33	1.33	0.67	0.17	1.33	1.33	0%
Best possible value	#	#	2	#	2	2	2	2	#
Result - Completeness	#	67%	67%	33%	67%	17%	#	#	#
Period B	Number of nodes	Number of ties	Average degrees	Weighted average degrees	Density	Weighted density	Partial average distance	Adjusted average distance	Particular room for distance improvement
Result - Value	3	4	1.33	2.67	0.67	0.13	1.33	1.33	0%
Best possible value	#	#	2	#	2	2	2	2	#
Result - Completeness	#	67%	67%	33%	67%	13%	#	#	#
Period C	Number of nodes	Number of ties	Average degrees	Weighted average degrees	Density	Weighted density	Partial average distance	Adjusted average distance	Particular room for distance improvement
Result - Value	4	12	3.00	12.00	3.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0%
Best possible value	#	22	2	22	2	2	2	2	#
Result - Completeness	#	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	#	#	#

'Problem box': If empty, there is no apparent issue

Period A	
Scale of relationships =	4
Period B	
Scale of relationships =	4
Period C	
Scale of relationships =	4

The lower part specifies the results for each individual actor and each period.

		Indicators at actor level																	
		Degrees			Weighted degrees			Density			Weighted density			Partial average distance			Adjusted average distance		
Sort	Actor	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort	Sort
Code		Period A	Period B	Period C	Period A	Period B	Period C	Period A	Period B	Period C	Period A	Period B	Period C	Period A	Period B	Period C	Period A	Period B	Period C
1																			
2	Example B	2	1	3	2	2	12	1.00	0.50	1.00	0.25	0.25	1.00	1.00	1.50	1.00	1.00	1.50	1.00
3	Example C	1	1	1	1	2	12	0.50	0.50	1.00	0.11	0.25	1.00	1.50	1.50	1.00	1.50	1.50	1.00
4	Example D	0	2	1	0	4	12	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
5	Example E	0	0	1	0	0	12	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
6																			
7																			
8																			
9																			
10																			
11																			

SECOND TAB - 'Sum_gph'

The tab "Sum_gph" indicates the key results for the three periods of time in the form of graphs. The indicators represented are the density and the partial distance.

